

USING ORIGINAL LITERATURE TO DEVELOP CRITICAL THINKING.

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Abstract

This article is devoted to the use of original literature, with the aim of developing critical thinking of university students. As many scientists believe, the development of critical thinking based on authentic literature has a positive effect on the training of future specialists.

Key words: Original literature, critical thinking, analytical, associative, logical, systemic thinking.

Introduction: In the process of globalization and development of the world community, the need to study foreign languages has increased dramatically. Modern pedagogy needs to rethink the changes in the educational space that have occurred in recent years and continue to this day. Society needs qualitatively new characteristics of pedagogical activity. At present, the higher education system has a tendency to develop critical thinking in students, since specialists with analytical skills and abilities are required who can recognize and solve problems.

Critical thinking is "a special kind of mental activity that allows a person to make a sound judgment about a point of view or model of behavior proposed to him" [Johnson, 1985, p.1].

"Critical thinking is a sequence of mental actions aimed at checking statements or systems of statements in order to determine their inconsistency with accepted facts, norms or values. ... There are levels of critical thinking, each of which has its own type of argumentation, characterized by different relationships between the logical and cognitive components:

- 1) empirical level - critical verification of facts;
- 2) theoretical level - critical verification of theories;
- 3) metatheoretical level - critical verification of norms and values"

"One of the main features of critical thinking is the obligatory presence of transcendental reflection, which requires the thinking subject to self-account for which of the functions of consciousness thinking is used: for value orientation, for cognition or for the search for means to achieve a goal."

"Critical thinking presupposes the skills of reflection regarding one's own mental activity, the ability to work with concepts, judgments, conclusions, questions, the development of abilities for analytical activity, as well as for assessing similar capabilities of other people. Critical thinking is generally characterized by a practical orientation. Due to this, it can be interpreted as a form of practical logic, considered within and depending on the context of reasoning and the individual characteristics of the reasoning subject."

"The mechanism of critical thinking includes mental operations that determine the process of reasoning and argumentation: setting a goal, identifying a problem, putting forward hypotheses, providing arguments, justifying them, predicting consequences, accepting or rejecting alternative points of view. It includes the ability to apply basic intellectual skills (knowledge and understanding) to synthesize, analyze and evaluate complex and ambiguous situations and problems. This includes the ability to identify a problem, clarify a situation, analyze arguments, study the issue from all angles, develop criteria for evaluating decisions and the reliability of information sources, and avoid generalizations."

"Critical thinking is the use of cognitive techniques or strategies that increase the likelihood of obtaining a desired end result. This definition characterizes thinking as something that is controlled, reasoned, and goal-directed - the kind of thinking that is used in problem solving, drawing conclusions, evaluating probabilities, and making decisions. In doing so, the thinker uses skills that are valid and effective for the specific situation and type of problem being solved."

Critical thinking is defined by the American Philosophical Association (APA) as: "purposeful, self-regulated judgment that culminates in interpretation, analysis, evaluation, and interaction, as well as an explanation of the evidential, conceptual, methodological, or contextual considerations on which the judgment is based."

Ideal critical thinking in humans is usually associated with curiosity, good knowledge, a reason for trust, open-mindedness, flexibility, fairness in evaluation, honesty in confronting personal prejudices, prudence in judgment, a willingness to reconsider and clarify problems and complex issues, thoroughness in seeking relevant information, reasonableness in choosing criteria, and a persistence in seeking results that are as accurate as the original sources used. This combination links the development of critical thinking skills with an understanding of the foundations of a rational and democratic society."

"Critical thinking is reflexive in nature and is related to communication, to the psychology of personality. It is connected not only with the cognitive sphere, but also with the motivational sphere, with self-awareness. When we deal not with people's thoughts, but with the phenomena of the material world, then ordinary thinking is quite sufficient for us."

As A.P. Korochensky rightly notes, "criticism is not limited to denial, to the disclosure of the nature of the negative and its transient nature. The evaluative nature of criticism means not only the ability to judge and reject through denial phenomena that have not withstood critical scrutiny ..., but is aimed even more at identifying in the course of critical knowledge and at affirming the positive."

At the same time, we realize that "good learners, good readers, monitor their understanding when they encounter new information. Good readers reread a piece of text if they no longer

understand it. Good listeners, when perceiving a message, usually ask questions or write down what they did not understand for future clarification. Passive learners usually ignore these problems in understanding. They are not aware of the confusion, misunderstandings, or even omissions of information that arise.”

Teachers who develop critical thinking in the classroom offer to consider various opinions, points of view on a problem, create conditions for the student to develop an independent opinion, solution, conclusion, “try to use all kinds of pair and group work in their classes, including debates and discussions, ... pay great attention to developing the qualities necessary for a productive exchange of opinions: tolerance, the ability to listen to others, responsibility for one’s own point of view.”

The development of critical thinking skills forms analytical, associative, logical, and systemic thinking in students of language universities, with subsequent application and development of these abilities in the field of professional activity. The ability to logically justify proposed solutions to a specific problem, analyze and synthesize specific facts, following a logical order of actions, is a priority in the professional training of future language specialists. In this regard, there is an urgent need to use original literature to develop critical thinking in university students. The problem of improving students' knowledge through the use of original texts is of interest to educators all over the world. The educational process has changed at different times in accordance with the requirements of the era and the level of state relations, but the issue of ways to improve knowledge has always remained relevant. Progressive ideas presented in the works of Zh.Zh. Zhalolov, G.T. Makhkamova, L.T. Akhmedova, Sh.S. Alimov, G.S. Altshuller, L.V. Vygotsky, G.K. Selevko, P. Bespalko, M.N. Guslova, N.D. Galskova and other scientists had a significant influence on the formation of the modern education system. The solution to the problem of the role of using authentic literature for the development of life of each member of society is based on the understanding of the phenomenon of education as a personal asset, as a process of familiarization with culture and as a special social institution. Education in the sense of personal asset affects the system of concepts, ideas, human relationships that determine and guide his behavior. Education as a process implies the degree of mastering the substantive part of culture, the influence and interaction of the individual and the entire cultural environment. Education from the point of view of a special social institution, being a component of the cultural environment of the individual, directs the impact of the training system on the formation and development of a person. The modern trend in the development of this problem is based on cooperation between the student and the teacher, developing new teaching strategies. The modern way of organizing the educational process is focused on preparing a student for a future profession and life in society, an individual who is able to analyze all events occurring in the world, think critically, and quickly adapt to changing living conditions, cooperate with other people, develop their creative potential and creative thinking. In order to consider the issue of using original texts in teaching, we will first turn to the concept of critical thinking. Critical thinking is a widely used term that includes the skills of identifying, analyzing, synthesizing, and evaluating information to make informed decisions [Halpern 2001: 273].

Although there is considerable debate over the interpretation of the definition of the term critical thinking, critical thinking has been identified as a top priority for foreign language teaching and learning in higher education. Despite the sustained interest in developing critical thinking in higher education, there is evidence that students lack the critical thinking and problem solving skills needed in today's workplaces. This shortcoming reveals the fact that English teachers do not fully understand the effectiveness of developing critical thinking and fail to use tasks to develop it in their

classes to the extent they should. The most adequate interpretation of the term critical thinking is provided by E. I. Fedotovskaya. According to the researcher, critical thinking is integrally linked to reflection on students' activities and includes the following characteristics of thinking [Fedotovskaya 2005:180]: analytical thinking (analysis of information, selection of necessary facts, comparison and contrast of facts or events); associative thinking (establishing associations with previously acquired material, familiar facts, events; establishing associations with new features of the subject), logical thinking (the ability to logically justify proposed solutions to a specific problem and follow a logical order of actions when presenting solutions), systemic thinking (the ability to analyze the object of study, the problem and its characteristics). As the researcher stated, critical thinking correlates with creative thinking. Creative thinking requires the implementation of the following abilities:

- 1) mental experimentation at the level of spatial perception;
- 2) independent application of knowledge to solve new tasks, problems and search for new solutions;
- 3) combinatorial abilities (the ability to combine previously known methods, ways of solving problems with a new, combined method);
- 4) abilities based on forecasting (the ability to foresee possible consequences after making decisions, to establish cause-and-effect relationships);
- 5) intuitive representation, insight (the ability to penetrate to the essence of the problem).

Given the close connection between critical and creative thinking, an attempt was made to formulate a definition of critical creative thinking as the ability and desire to evaluate different statements and make objective judgments based on well-founded evidence, the ability to see gaps in arguments and not succumb to statements that do not have sufficient grounds.

Prospective modern education systems should provide an opportunity for each person to use the right to education that he or she wants. As can be seen from the above characteristics of critical and creative thinking, these two types of thinking are closely interconnected. The first necessary condition for the cognitive process is the ability to analyze facts that require explanation. Students with well-developed critical thinking can freely construct questions and think unconventionally. While for students with low critical thinking skills, all the events described seem obvious, based on the facts of the original material read.

Unfortunately, this kind of formulation cannot be considered successful, since it is practically no different from the definitions of simply critical thinking that we have given earlier. After all, if critical thinking presupposes the development of analytical, associative, logical, combinatorial, systemic and independent thinking, then creative thinking brings to the forefront the development of abilities for imagination, virtual experimentation, intuitive forecasting.

Considering that “creativity is an activity that generates something qualitatively new and unique,” we will take the liberty of offering our own formulation:

Critical creative thinking in relation to the media system and media texts is a complex reflexive process of thinking that includes associative perception, synthesis, analysis and evaluation of the mechanisms of functioning of media in society and media texts (information/messages), in combination with audiovisual imagination, virtual experimentation, logical and intuitive forecasting in the media sphere.

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